

GOAL ARCHITECTURE AND TRANSITION STRATEGY FOR THE DEFENSE INFORMATION SYSTEM NETWORK

William F. Vogelzang
Defense Information Systems Agency

Ronald A. Hodge
Booz-Allen & Hamilton Inc.

Abstract

The goal integrated communications architecture for the Defense Information System Network (DISN) is based on open systems principles and will support multimedia workstations and multi-level security applications. Broadband Integrated Services Digital Network (BISDN) standards and services form the basic infrastructure of the goal architecture. This paper provides a transition framework to economically and efficiently transition from today's communications architecture to the goal architecture in a phased approach. The trend is toward information sharing, consolidation, and integrated services (e.g., voice, data, video, and imagery) while capitalizing on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) services and equipment. The path to the future environment is characterized as a controlled evolutionary transition strategy based on anticipated changes in user requirements, advances in technology, and the pace of standards implementation.

Introduction

The Defense Information Systems Agency's (DISA's) role has expanded to include global information processing and information transfer services via the Defense Information System (DIS). DISA has established the Corporate Information Management (CIM) initiative to ensure that effective business management principles, processes, procedures, and practices are used to achieve the information service goals of the DIS. The DIS is defined as the worldwide aggregation of all mobile and fixed DoD information systems, including sensors, data entry devices, communications networks, computer resources, facilities, and operational and support staff that are organized to provide protection, collection, production, storage, dissemination, and display of information for the DoD (ref. 1). DISN is a subset of DIS and provides the end-to-end information transfer and value-added network services for the common-user portion of DIS (i.e., networking and communications). The DISN is the telecommunications infrastructure that is transparent to its users, facilitates the management of information resources, and is responsive to national security and defense needs under all conditions in the most efficient manner. Although certain C² systems are not within the domain of the DISN now, the vision for the future DISN includes the DoD information transfer system that will provide the communications infrastructure and services needed to satisfy National Defense command, control, communications, and intelligence (C³I) requirements and support the CIM initiative.

The Telecommunications Environment

The environment for 1995-2005 telecommunications is characterized by the available telecommunications resources (current and planned); the stresses under which telecommunications must support requirements; the mission and functions supported; the size of user population receiving services and support; and other external factors such as technology, policies, and budgets. Exhibit 1 depicts this environment and its principal systems and networks. The levels of conflict (i.e., peacetime, crisis and conventional war [overseas], early transattack, and massive nuclear attack and post attack) determine the DoD systems requirements. DISN includes long-haul communications, local telecommunications infrastructure, CINC and MILDEP telecommunication systems supporting nuclear deterrence and warfighting capabilities, and value added service offerings (e.g., directory). The DISN must interoperate with civil and commercial systems, North Atlantic treaty Organization (NATO)/allied systems, and special systems such as those developed to support National Security and Emergency Preparedness (NS/EP) users.

The user population refers to four broad user groups whose missions and activities are most critical to carrying out the military roles that support national security objectives. These groups, listed in order of increasing size, include the National Command Authority (NCA), the military command structure, the military warfighting forces, and the military support structure and forces. The reduced conventional war threat in Europe will be the most striking change in the 1990s. This change is expected to result in a reduction of in-place military forces and a repositioning of U.S. communications assets. Forces in the European theater will rely more on interoperation with indigenous telecommunications assets. To compensate for fewer in-theater bases, the DoD must be able to move deployable systems, such as telecommunication assets, into unequipped bases.

This concept already applies to other areas of the world where the United States does not have a military presence. General downsizing of the military and maintaining the capability to place forces in a fast-response mode require telecommunications assets that can be installed, operated, and maintained with less manpower. Therefore, telecommunications assets must be automated, experience much longer mean-time-between-failures (MTBF), and use more standardized equipment (e.g., increased integration).

50.1.1

**Exhibit 1
DISN Environment**

Because of these technical advances, training in deployment of planned new technologies and interoperability must be increased. Modeling and simulation will be extensively used for joint training of distributed stateside forces that require high-capacity networks. Because special operations forces will account for a larger proportion of the military capability, smaller, lighter, and very reliable telecommunications and processing equipment must be available that can be installed and operated easily.

Despite these demands for increased automation, reliability, integration, deployability, and interoperability, fewer budgetary resources are expected to be available for developing highly specialized DoD equipment. Therefore, commercial telecommunications products are likely to be adapted to meet DoD requirements, and military-unique features of surge capacity, security, precedence, and survivability will have to be incorporated into commercial network subsystems.

Telecommunications Objectives

The description of the operational environment reflects the expected geopolitical context and military strategy of the 1990s and post-2000 years. The objectives for telecommunications systems and services take into account the impact of this changing environment on today's telecommunications facilities. The objectives relate to specific requirements in the areas of traffic capacity, survivability, and security. Objectives for DoD telecommunications (regardless of system size, survivability, or technology base) include the following:

- Ability to adapt and grow with changing user requirements
- Increased interoperation with non-DoD networks through adoption of common standards
- Increased need for reliability and maintainability
- Use of more automation to reduce the number of support personnel
- Increased use of commercial products and their derivatives to lower development costs and achieve economies of scale.

Goal Architecture

The goal architecture provides the technical and economic planning objectives for future decision making. This goal architecture, which is intentionally high level to reflect desired capabilities, is a substructure of the overall DIS infrastructure. Although technologies and systems other than those specified for the goal architecture may be required to meet unique user needs, describing a homogeneous environment will enable DISA to focus decision making to ensure a consistent, evolutionary approach to future DISN services and systems.

A broadband ISDN (BISDN) based goal architecture was determined through a review of planned and emerging technologies as they relate to DoD technical and economic objectives. BISDN offers opportunities for DoD to lower communications costs, reduce the inventory of disparate

50.1.2

networks and dedicated facilities, and provide advanced services. BISDN will expand the set of ISDN services and features. Exhibit 2 presents the components of the goal architecture and identifies the "pure" BISDN components in the DoD network. Typically, BISDN terminals are multimedia, multi-level secure (MLS) workstations; video terminals; ADP processing centers; sensors; and other computing resources. The exhibit does not show high-speed LANs and metropolitan area networks (MANs), ISDN PBXs and network interfaces (e.g., civil, tactical, NATO) that can be accommodated and interfaced with the BISDN access node.

BISDN access nodes can be implemented in a high-density user region and be a shared resource in the region. Exhibit 3 illustrates this construct and the wide area network transport. Note that the wide area network is a mix of public and private network resources that meet specific needs of the DoD user communities. The exhibit also suggests that network management and control will be distributed across local, regional, and global domains of the network. Essentially, each community of interest has its own virtual network over which it can exercise management and control. This capability is bounded by the higher levels of management and control to ensure fairness in the network.

Goal Architecture Standards

Standards for the goal architecture follow the standards for BISDN and anticipated application layer services. Current standards for BISDN are limited to layers 1 and 2 (physical and link layers). The CCITT 1992 and 1996 standards meetings should complete the higher layer standards associated with BISDN. Exhibit 4 shows the extent of known and anticipated standards for the goal architecture (ref. 1).

General Transition Strategy

A controlled transition from today's telecommunications environment to the goal architecture must take into account the following factors:

- Unsatisfied user needs
- Availability of new technology and services
- Standards approval and availability
- Economic life of current networks and facilities
- Contract expiration dates
- Cost/affordability in a declining budget environment
- Changing geopolitical environment.

The fundamental transition strategy is to use telecommunications economically in the near term without jeopardizing certain military-unique requirements such as security, assured service, and survivability. As opportunities arise, new technology, services, and standards must be exploited based on their projected availability. Near-term initiatives should not preclude future options that lead to the

desired goal architecture. This general strategy is constrained by certain real-world events such as the key factors outlined above. The near-term DISN initiatives include integrating private MILDEP and agency T1/T3 networks and introducing a pilot high-speed packet overlay network. This initiative provides cost savings in transmission and increased capacity for packet services. Establishing a test-bed/pilot to include SONET/ATM transport capabilities will set the stage for acquiring services in the mid-term time frame by providing experience in the operational aspects of this type of network.

The mid-term wide area transition will provide a transport infrastructure similar to that portrayed in Exhibit 3 along with a narrowband network that provides switched voice, data, and imagery (including video) services (Px64 increments for office and meeting room applications). Other services will be supported much as they are today except that they will use the SONET transport. (ATM would be phased in gradually and be used selectively.) The transport will provide directory services and network management (at various levels). Exhibit 5 portrays the general strategy outlined above for the wide area network. Many lease and implementation options should be pursued through system engineering studies.

Conclusions

Comprehensive investment strategies should be developed to support the transition to the goal architecture. While the near term reflects a continued growth in data services, increasing digital connectivity, the opportunities for significant transition from today's systems will be most evident in the midterm. The midterm introduces many goal architecture services, such as messaging, directory, high-speed data transfer, and desktop video. It also includes integrated (voice/data/imagery) workstations, ATM/SONET network interfaces, and an expansion of commercial services utilization. Successful evolution to the goal architecture requires broad DoD consensus and commitment. A jointly developed transition strategy ensures consistency of standards and technologies.

References

1. DISA/JIEO. *Defense Information System Network Goal Architecture and Transition Strategy (Final Report)*. June 1992.

**Exhibit 2
Goal DISN Elements**

**Exhibit 3
DISN Transport Levels**

50.1.4

EXHIBIT 4
Goal Architecture Standards

Layer	Standards
7 Application	FTAM, VT, CCITT X.400, X.500, CMIP, MSP
6 Presentation	Presentation Layer Protocols
5 Session	Session Layer Protocols
4 Transport	Transport Layer Protocols TPO, TP4, SP4
3 Network	BISDN Network Layer Protocol ISDN Q.931, SP3
2 Data Link	ATM, AAL ISDN LAPD
1 Physical	SONET, ISDN CCITT I.430, I.431

ATM	Asynchronous Transfer Mode	MSP	Message Security Protocol
AAL	ATM Adaption Layer	SONET	Synchronous Optical Network
CMIP	Common Management Information Protocol	SP3	Secure Protocol - Layer 3
FTAM	File Transfer, Access, and Management	SP4	Secure Protocol - Layer 4
ISDN	Integrated Services Digital Network	VT	Virtual Terminal
LAPD	Link Access Procedure D	X.400	Message Handling System
LLC	Link Layer Control	X.500	Directory Service

EXHIBIT 5
General Transition Strategy for Wide Area Networks

